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NEW RECORDS OF THE GENERA *ASTRENIS* AND *PHRUDUS* (HYMENOPTERA, ICHNEUMONIDAE: *PHRUDUS* GROUP) FROM UKRAINE

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Varga, O. New records of genera *Astrenis* and *Phrudus* (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae: *Phrudus* group) from Ukraine. — In this paper, two species of the *Phrudus* group of genera, *Astrenis paradoxus* (Schmiedeknecht, 1907) and *Phrudus compressus* Vikberg, 2000, are recorded from Ukraine for the first time. Images and short diagnoses of the recorded species are provided.

Key words: Darwin wasps, parasitoids, new records, Ukrainian Carpathians.

Варга, О. Нові знахідки з родів *Astrenis* та *Phrudus* (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae: *Phrudus* group) в Україні. — Уперше для України зазначено два види з групи родів, близьких до *Phrudus*, а саме *Astrenis paradoxus* (Schmiedeknecht, 1907) та *Phrudus compressus* Vikberg, 2000. Ці види проілюстровано та надано короткі порівняльні діагнози.

Ключові слова: їздці-іхневмоніди, паразитоїди, нові знахідки, Українські Карпати.

Introduction

The genera *Astrenis* Förster, 1869 and *Phrudus* Förster, 1869 are small Darwin wasp groups (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) containing only seven and eleven species, respectively (Chiu & Wong, 1987; Vikberg & Koponen, 2000; Yu *et al.*, 2016); of them five species altogether have been recorded from Ukraine so far (Varga, 2023, 2024).

Both genera were classically placed in the subfamily Phrudinae (Townes, 1971), while more recent phylogenetic analyses (Quicke *et al.*, 2009) grouped these genera with the members of the subfamily Tersilochinae (as so-called *Phrudus* group). However, there is still much uncertainty regarding of these relationships (Bennett *et al.*, 2019).

The members of the *Phrudus* group are endoparasitoids of different coleopterans (Gunthart, 1949; Franz, 1958; Bennett *et al.*, 2019).

Material and Methods

The voucher specimens used in this study were collected with a sweeping net by the author in the Ukrainian Carpathians and adjacent territories in 2022 and 2025, in particular in the coniferous mountain forest near m. Vysoka (Gorgany) and deciduous lowland forest near Ivano-Frankivsk. The specimens are deposited in the collection of the Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv (SIZK). Images were taken using a Leica

Z16 APO microscope equipped with Leica FLEXACAM C1 camera and processed by LAS Core software at SIZK.

***Astrenis paradoxus* (Schmiedeknecht, 1907) (Figs 1–4)**

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk Region, Zahvizdya, deciduous forest, sweeping, 48.94340, 24.62228, 06.06.2025, 1 ♀ (O. Varga) (SIZK).

Diagnosis. This species can be distinguished from congeners by the combination of the following characters: head and metasoma (except first tergite) brownish yellow (Figs 1–3); fore tarsal claw pectinate to the apex, with subequal teeth; antenna with 16 flagellomeres; hind coxa rugose (Fig. 3).

Figs 1–4. *Astrenis paradoxus* (Schmiedeknecht, 1907): 1 – habitus in lateral view, 2 – head in frontal view, 3 – propodeum and metasomal tergites 1–2 in dorsal view, 4 – wings. Scale bars: 0.5 mm (1) and 0.1 mm (2–4).

Distribution. France, Germany, Sweden, United Kingdom (Vikberg & Koponen, 2000), and Ukraine (**first record**).

***Phrudus compressus* Vikberg, 2000** (Figs 5–8)

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk Region, Gorgany, slopes of m. Vysoka, 48.611402, 24.097001, 1000–1500 m, sweeping, 18–23.07.2022, 1 ♀ (O. Varga) (SIZK).

Diagnosis. This species can be distinguished from congeners by the combination of the following characters:

head and mesosoma not strongly compressed laterally; antenna with 14–16 flagellomeres, flagellomeres 4–5 each with a white tooth-like projection on the basal 0.2–0.3 of the flagellomere; propodeum with carinae present, but weak, area petiolaris long, at least 1.4 times as long as maximum width (Fig. 7); fore wing with vein 3rs-m present anteriorly (Fig. 8); metasoma laterally compressed, second tergite at least 1.4 times as long as maximum width

Figs 5–8. *Phrudus compressus* Vikberg, 2000: 5 – habitus in lateral view, 6 – head in frontal view, 7 – propodeum and metasomal tergites 1–2 in dorsal view, 8 – wings. Scale bars: 0.5 mm (5) and 0.1 mm (6–8).

(Fig. 7). For comparison of the closely related species, *P. defectus* Stelfox, 1966, see Fig. 5 in Varga (2023).

Distribution. Described from the Nordic countries (Finland and Sweden) (Vikberg & Koponen, 2000), Ukraine (**first record**).

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